

Comparative Analysis of Compound Words in English and Uzbek

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Annotation: The word compound means one thing that is composed of two or more elements. When you hear the word compound, you might think of a chemical compound, compound interest, or you might just use the word as a synonym for a mixture. Compounding is also a grammatical phenomenon, and there is a lengthy list of compound words in the English language. This article discusses on the Comparative analysis of compound words in English and Uzbek.

Keywords: Compound words; comparative analysis; grammatical phenomenon; philology.

Simply put, compound capacity one issue made of many things. The definition for compound phrases skill simply that. Compound words: two or greater phrases joined to create a new meaning. Compound words are not two random words thrust together. Compound phrases will be two words that are frequently observed together, such as late-night, nice-looking, or seafood. Compound words are normally two base phrases used together. Remember, base phrases are standalone words that sign a particular meaning, even when stripped of affixes (example: success in successful).

That's not to say, however, that compound words can't use derived words. Derived words are words that are built on a root, typically with the addition of an affix (example: teach + er = teacher). Many compound words include derived words (coffee maker, sewing machine, skyscraper). The manner of compounding is unique from derivation and inflection — each of which normally contain including an affix to exchange a word's grammatical category. While derivation, inflection, and compounding are all a system for creating new words, compounding makes use of two base words, instead than a single base phrase and an affix (e.g., -ing, im-, or -ed). Compounds help us recognize phrases as a single unit, which in some cases helps to make clear the meaning of a phrase or phrase in English. Using a hyphen right here indicates the reader that the words vegan and pleasant ought to be taken as a single unit. Otherwise, it may be read as, "Let's seem to be for a vegan friendly restaurant," with vegan and friendly being two specific adjectives to describe a restaurant. When new things, ideas, or phrases come into the collective focus of the public, they need a title or some thing people can say to refer to them. Compounding words is one of the most (if not the most) common sorts of phrase formation in English because it is so easy to do. These new phrases can be figurative like chairman (the head of a committee or group, not a chair-shaped man), or really a mixture of the meaning of each of the base words, like lighthouse (a residence of light). The word email wasn't used till the late twentieth century because email, or digital mail, didn't exist until then. There was a need to create a word to talk this new notion of sending a message electronically, and e mail —which grew to become email, besides the hyphen — was once a simple option.

In Uzbek, two independent phrases are linked in a positive grammatical form, and there is a grammatical connection between the compound words. This connection consequences in a syntactic unit, a phrase, or a sentence, now not a lexeme. We ought to bear in idea the fact. In most compounds the rightmost morpheme determines the category of the whole word. Thus, greenhouse is a noun due to the fact its rightmost element is a noun, spoonfeed is a verb due to the fact feed additionally belongs to this category. "English orthography is not regular in representing compounds, which are sometimes written as single words, sometimes with an intervening hyphen, and sometimes as separate words. In terms of pronunciation, however, there is an essential generalization to be made. A second

distinguishing feature of compounds in English is that anxious and plural markers can't normally be attached to the first element, even though they can be added to the compound as a whole. (There are some exceptions, however, such as passers-by and parks supervisor.)

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